

ACTION OF SODIUM ON ETHYL β METHYL BUTANE- $\alpha,\beta\beta$ -TRICARBOXYLATE. PART IV

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The Dieckmann condensation product of ethyl β -methylbutane- $\alpha,\beta\beta$ -tricarboxylate on treatment with ethyl bromoacetate furnishes ethyl 4-methylcyclopentan-1-one-2:4-dicarboxylate-2-acetate as the only isolable product. This on hydrolysis and reduction can be smoothly converted into 1-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxylic-3-acetic acid, m.p. 124-25°. An independent synthesis of this latter from ethyl 3-methylcyclopentan-1-one-3-carboxylate by an adaptation of Ruzicka's method (*Ber.*, 1917, 60, 1362) is also described.

In previous parts of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20 173, 189) it has been shown that the product of the Dieckmann condensation of ethyl β -methylbutane- $\alpha,\beta\beta$ -tricarboxylate on alkylation furnishes solely the ester (I) and not the isomeric ester (II).

In conformity with this view it is now found that the initial sodio derivative formed in the condensation on treatment with ethyl bromoacetate gives ethyl 4-methylcyclopentan-1-one-2:4-dicarboxylate-2-acetate (I, R = CH₂·CO₂Et). The constitution of the latter follows from the fact that on hydrolysis with hydrochloric acid it furnishes 4-methylcyclopentan-1-one-4-carboxylic-2-acetic acid (III), which has been purified through the ethyl ester, b.p. 145°/6 mm. The latter on reduction with amalgamated zinc and concentrated hydrochloric acid according to Clemmensen's method gives 1-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxylic-3-acetic acid (IV), m.p. 124-25°, identical with a synthetic specimen prepared from ethyl 3-methylcyclopentan-1-one-3-carboxylate (Ruzicka, *Ber.*, 1917, 60, 1362) through the following stages:

Reference should be made in this connection to the work of Banerjee (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 223) who investigated the action of ethyl β -chloropropionate on the sodio derivative described above, and on the basis of Baker's work (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1548) formulated the

product as (II, $R = CH_2 \cdot CH \cdot CO_2Et$). The latter on successive hydrolysis and reduction is found to give the dicarboxylic acid (V), which on ketonisation according to Dieckmann's method gives a bicyclic ketone which is believed to be 7-methyl-0:3-bicyclooctane-1-one (VI), since on oxidation with nitric acid it gives impure *trans*-1-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxylic-2-acetic acid, m.p. 126-27°. Apparently no direct comparison was made with authentic specimens of the *cis*- and *trans*-modifications of 1-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxylic-2-acetic acid, m.p. 110° and 139° respectively (Linstead and Lirington, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 668; also Barnett, Cook and Linstead, *ibid.*, 1935, 1068).

There can be little doubt, however, that Banerjee's acid, m.p. 126°, is in reality 1-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxylic-3-acetic acid, m.p. 124-25°, described above and the bicyclic ketone from which it is formed on oxidation should, therefore, be represented by the alternative formula (VII) and the initial product of the condensation will have the modified formula (I, $R = CH_2 \cdot CH_2 \cdot CO_2Et$).

This brings the above series of reactions into line with the view developed in these series of papers regarding the course pursued by the sodium condensation of ethyl β -methylbutane- $\alpha\beta$ -tricarboxylate. Further work regarding the correctness of the above view of the constitution of the ketone (VII) will shortly be published.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl 4-Methylcyclopentan-1-one-2:4-dicarboxylate-2-acetate (I, $R = CH_2 \cdot CO_2Et$).—Ethyl β -methylbutane- $\alpha\beta$ -tricarboxylate (21.1 g.) was heated on the water-bath for 1 hour with a fine suspension of sodium (2.06 g.) in benzene (50 c.c.). The clear solution, thus obtained, was cooled in ice and ethyl bromoacetate (10 c.c.) added to it and kept overnight. It was then refluxed on the water-bath for 24 hours. When cold the product was treated with water, the benzene layer was separated and the aqueous layer was extracted once with ether. The benzene-etheral extract was washed with water and the benzene evaporated. The residual oil was then distilled under diminished pressure when ethyl 4-methylcyclopentan-1-one-2:4-dicarboxylate-2-acetate (I, $R = CH_2 \cdot CO_2Et$) was obtained as a colourless mobile liquid, b.p. 170°/5 mm., yield 21 g. It gave no colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 58.5; H, 7.3; $C_{15}H_{24}O_7$ requires C, 58.5; H, 7.3 per cent).

4'-Methylcyclopentan-1-one-4-carboxylic-2-acetic Acid (III).—The above keto-tricarboxylic ester (20 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing on a sand-bath for 20 hours with concentrated hydrochloric acid (100 c.c.). The oily liquid went into solution in about 2 hours. The solution was evaporated to dryness on the water-bath. The crude acid (12 g.) was heated on the water-bath for 12 hours with absolute alcohol (50 c.c.) and 5 c.c. of alcoholic hydrogen chloride (saturated at 0°). The alcohol was then distilled off. The liquid remaining was treated with water and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution

and water and dried over anhydrous calcium chloride. The solvent was then evaporated and the residual oil distilled under reduced pressure when ethyl 4-methylcyclopentan-1-one-4-carboxylate-2-acetate (as III) was obtained boiling at $145^{\circ}/6$ mm., yield 10 g. (Found: C, 60.6; H, 7.7. $C_{13}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 60.9; H, 7.8 per cent).

1-Methylcyclopentane-1-carboxylic-3-acetic Acid (IV).—Ethyl 4-methylcyclopentan-1-one-4-carboxylate-2-acetate (5.5 g.) was heated on a sand-bath for 30 hours with concentrated hydrochloric acid (45 c.c.) and zinc (60 g.) previously amalgamated by keeping in contact with 5% mercuric chloride solution for an hour. More hydrochloric acid (50 c.c. in all) was added from time to time. The clear solution was saturated with salt and extracted repeatedly with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with water and the ether was then evaporated. The residual liquid for the most part solidified on keeping in a vacuum desiccator. It was filtered at the pump and washed with cold water. The residue after one crystallisation from water melted at $116-17^{\circ}$ but after several crystallisations the melting point rose up to $124-25^{\circ}$ and did not change on further crystallisations. Moreover, the mixed melting point of this acid with a sample of the same acid, prepared as described below, by a modification of Ruzicka's method (*loc. cit.*), was also $124-25^{\circ}$. (Found: C, 57.7; H, 7.5. $C_9H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 58.0; H, 7.5 per cent).

Synthesis of 1-Methylcyclopentane-1-carboxylic-3-acetic acid (IV) (by a modification of Ruzicka's method).—The mixture of unsaturated and hydroxy esters as obtained by the condensation of ethyl bromoacetate with ethyl 3-methylcyclopentan-1-ol-2-carboxylate (5 g.) in presence of zinc was heated on the water-bath for 3 hours with $\frac{1}{2}$ molecule of phosphorus oxychloride and 3 volumes of dry benzene. It was then treated with ice-water, the benzene layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted with ether. The benzene-ethereal extract was washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution and water and the solvent was then evaporated. A mixture of the unsaturated esters was obtained, boiling at $125^{\circ}/4$ mm., on distillation of the residual oil, yield 2.5 g.

The mixture of unsaturated esters (2.5 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (16 c.c.) and shaken in an atmosphere of pure hydrogen at the room temperature and under atmospheric pressure in presence of platinum oxide (0.2 g.) till the absorption of hydrogen was complete. In half an hour 80% of the calculated amount of hydrogen was absorbed, and it took 16 hours for the absorption of the rest. The alcoholic solution was then filtered and the alcohol evaporated. The residual liquid was hydrolysed by heating on the water-bath for 2 hours with excess of 10% aqueous alcoholic caustic potash. The alcohol was then evaporated with the addition of water and the solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid and extracted repeatedly with ether. On evaporation of the ether a liquid residue was obtained which solidified partly on keeping in a vacuum desiccator. It was filtered at the pump and washed with a little cold water. The solid product, thus obtained, on crystallisation from water melted at $116-18^{\circ}$ (as described by Ruzicka) but after three crystallisations attained a constant melting point, $124-25^{\circ}$.

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